

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

POMEGRANATE AS A VALUABLE BIOLOGICALLY RAW MATERIAL FOR FOOD FOR THE NEEDS OF THE FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L.) is a fruit rich in biologically active compounds that contains bio-waste (peel and seeds) that can potentially be converted into products for a wide range of applications. Recent studies have demonstrated the powerful antioxidant and antimicrobial effects of using pomegranate peel and seeds as natural food additives, which has prompted researchers to use them in bioplastics and edible coatings for food packaging. In addition, these components have a strong plasticizing effect on packaging materials, while simultaneously prolonging the shelf life of food products due to active packaging. Pomegranate seed oil and its biologically active compounds were particularly effective in combating the effects of ultraviolet light on the skin of animals and on in vitro models, where cells and microorganisms are separated from the whole organism. They also promote wound healing and have pronounced anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antibacterial properties. Of particular interest are pomegranate ingredients, which are already mass-produced and presented in the markets of pomegranate ingredients for health. In this article, just a brief overview of the latest technological and product innovations in this area is given to help innovation managers choose the right direction in accordance with the conditions and objectives of the business.

Keywords: pomegranate, processing into juice, solid fruit residues, complex processing, food additives, medicinal extracts.

The demands for fruits and processed products have significantly increased following the surging human population growth and rising health awareness [1-2]. However, an enormous amount of fruit waste is generated during their production life-cycle due to the inedible portion and perishable nature, which become a considerable burden to the environment. Embracing the concept of “circular economy”, these fruit wastes represent sustainable and renewable resources and can be integrated into biorefinery platforms for valorization into a wide range of high-value products [3].

Currently, pomegranates are in great demand because of their beneficial properties and health benefits, due to the increasing popularity of pomegranate, there is an increase in both demand and prices for this fruit. Currently, pomegranates can be found at a higher price than other fruits, such as oranges. They are a good source of antioxidants and vitamins, including vitamin C.

In addition, this fruit is a good source of dietary fiber, which helps reduce the risk of heart and other chronic diseases. Pomegranates, thanks to their antioxidant properties, help fight some forms of cancer. Pomegranate juice helps to improve the lipid profile and reverse the aging of the arteries.

Most of the pomegranate production on the world market falls in regions where winter temperatures do not exceed 28 degrees Celsius, and a good annual harvest can be about 1,000 tons. Pomegranates have a long shelf life and can be stored at room temperature for up to four weeks or frozen for up to six months. Fruits are used in various dishes around the world, including in sweet pastries (in France), in obtaining ice

cream (in Italy), in making jam (in Israel) and as delicacies of the month of Ramadan (in Saudi Arabia). It is also used as a natural sweetener in many countries such as India and Pakistan.

Manufacturers of cosmetics and skin care products are showing increasing interest in pomegranate as a natural ingredient. Pomegranate is an excellent source of antioxidants, vitamins C and E and other essential nutrients that improve the appearance of the skin. Manufacturers of sunscreens are also interested in using pomegranate juice because it provides protection from UV damage without causing irritation or excessive dryness.

Pomegranate juice contains compounds called polyphenols, which absorb the energy of ultraviolet radiation and turn it into heat instead of harmful light rays. It is rich in antioxidants that can help in the treatment of cardiovascular diseases, juice has been and remains the main product of pomegranate processing. It is used directly and as part of various food and beverages, including pastries, jams, confectionery.

According to SkyQuest Technology Consulting Pvt. [4], the global garnet market in 2021 was estimated at \$24.8 billion. This is 5.3% more than last year. In physical terms, the industry produced a total of 3.0 million tons in 2021, compared with 2.8 million tons in 2020. China remains the leading producer of pomegranates, followed by India. These two countries, as well as Iran, Turkey and the United States, are collectively responsible for 76% of global production. Worldwide, more than 300,000 hectares of land have been allocated for the cultivation of pomegranate. The global pomegranate market is expected to reach USD

33.86 billion by 2028, with an average annual growth rate of 5.3% during the forecast period (2022-2028).

As the global production of pomegranate juice increases, the amount of peel and seeds remaining after its production also increases [5], which actualized the problem of their efficient processing.

Moreover, competition in the world markets of pomegranate juices has now grown, and the demand for biologically active ingredients of pomegranate peel and seeds remaining after their receipt is growing all the time.

The technological scheme for the production of commercial pomegranate juices is a flexible model that allows you to involve secondary raw materials in processing and get value-added products from it [6].

Taking into account these trends, it is the organization of processing of secondary raw materials right on the spot as it is formed in the process of obtaining juice that is now considered as the main trend for improving the economic condition of food sector enterprises with specialization in the processing of pomegranate fruits [7].

Background of the issue

At the plants for the production of pomegranate juices, more solid residues in the form of fruit peel and their seeds are formed than the juices themselves, while there are still no ready-made multifunctional lines for deep processing of this type of waste in the markets of technological equipment. Therefore, at most of these plants, technical progress is still developing one-sidedly, in the direction of only improving the quality of juice [8].

However, the history of this issue shows that such lines can be designed to order.

Back in 1986, at the Geokchay juice Factory (now AZNAR), a line of the Italian company Bertuzzi was put into operation for drying the peel of pomegranate fruits, cyclic extraction with water at a hydromodule of 1:4 at ambient temperature or when heated to 100 ° C and evaporation of the resulting extracts. In total, there were eight autoclaves connected by pipelines in the line. The first cycle began with loading the peel into these autoclaves, which had previously been processed in a drying apparatus. After that, pumps were turned on to pump water from the first pair of extractors to the second, from the second to the third, from the third to the fourth. This process was carried out in several cycles until the entire stock of hydrophilic components of the peel was exhausted. At the end of each cycle, the extraction was sent to the collection of the total extract, from the collection to a centrifuge for cleaning from relatively large suspensions and then to the apparatus, where it was evaporated to a significant thickening to obtain a concentrated aqueous extract of the peel called "tannin" [9].

Since this so-called tannin, which was a thick viscous liquid of dark brown color, contained not only polyphenols, but also a significant amount of simple sugars, acids and viscous biocolloids, it became too viscous, which made it difficult to work with it.

Taking this into account, it was proposed to process the peel according to a multi-product scheme, which was based on the same drying, grinding and

cyclic extraction of raw materials with a hydromodule of 1:4, but not only with clean water and not all the time, but in three time stages and with a change of solvent. In the first stage – with water at 35 ° C for 6 hours in 12 cycles with centrifugation of the formed extracts and their treatment with a 1% gelatin solution to obtain a tannin and liquid tannin in the sediment - the product of concentration of the remaining transparent part of the extract. In the second stage - in 6 cycles of 30 minutes each: in the first cycle - with water acidified with citric acid, with a raw material/water/acid ratio of 1:4:0.21 at 90-95 ° C for 1 hour; in all other cycles - with water at 75-80 ° C, with centrifugation of separated extracts and processing their ethanol with the production of pectin and food coloring in the precipitate – the product of concentrating the remaining transparent part of the extract. In the third stage - in 12 cycles of 30 minutes each with 0.1% sodium hydroxide solution with the treatment of the formed HCL extracts and obtaining a mixture of alkaline-soluble polyphenols with nitrogenous substances - the product of drying and grinding the precipitate [10].

Georgian authors proposed to use pomegranate peel in the production of aqueous and alcoholic extracts; syrup - dye; cognac "Pomegranate" with its enrichment with tannins of the peel by the accelerated method; additives for the perfume and cosmetic industry [11].

The Uzbek authors came to the conclusion that the processing of by-products of pomegranate juice production can provide additional profit, whereas their simple burial in a landfill is associated with an increase in non-production costs and environmental pollution [12].

A technology has been developed for producing a powdered product from pomegranate peel, which has the potential for use in medicine, the leather and dyeing industry, as well as in the preparation of tooth powder. It was found that the yield of this powder product is 15.5% of the weight of the fruit and or 34% of the weight of the peel [13].

These and other researchers agree that there are all prerequisites for the establishment of the processing of bio-waste of this type into products with added value and a long shelf life.

Industrially applied developments

Manufacturers of cosmetics and skin care products are interested in using pomegranate juice because of its antioxidant properties. These properties help protect the skin from damage caused by free radicals. Free radicals can cause the appearance of wrinkles and age spots, so the use of products containing antioxidants is necessary to preserve the youth and health of the skin. Pomegranate juice contains lactic acid, which helps to tighten the skin and reduce the appearance of cellulite. Pomegranate fruit contains antioxidants that help reduce redness and inflammation associated with acne scars. In addition, pomegranate juice can help reduce the amount of oil produced by skin cells. This helps to keep the pores clean and reduces the risk of acne scars reappearing.

Considering this, some cosmetic companies have started to include lipophilic extracts of pomegranate

seeds in their products. L'Oreal Paris has launched a line of facial moisturizers that include pomegranate extract, and Estee Lauder uses it as an ingredient in its new line of sunscreens.

Dataintelo has published a report entitled "Pomegranate Powder Market Research Report" [14], which predicts that the size of the global market for the Pomegranate Powder product will grow by an average of 5.8% during the period from 2022 to 2030 and by an average of 5.8% during the forecast period. The growth can be attributed to the high demand for baked goods and juice drinks containing pomegranate powder in regions such as North America and Europe. This product has been recognized as a healthy ingredient, which has led to its wider use in other products such as jams and others, especially in the Asia-Pacific region, where people have moved from traditional recipes to more balanced alternative foods.

Pomegranate powder is a powdered form of pomegranate, which is dried and crushed into fine particles. It has several health benefits, including antioxidant properties that protect the body from free radicals.

Depending on the type, the market is divided into "Spray Drying Pomegranate Powder" (Spray Drying Pomegranate Powder) and "Lyophilized Pomegranate Powder".

Spray Drying Pomegranate Powder is a spray-dried powder that contains the same amount of antioxidants as fresh pomegranates. It tastes and colors similar to fresh fruit powders. It does not contain additives or preservatives, but it may not have a long shelf life because it does not require chemical stabilization.

Freeze-dried pomegranate powder is obtained by removing moisture from freeze-dried fruits at low temperatures. This drying process preserves most of the nutrients and taste characteristics, having a minimal effect on the color. Nativas Organics Organic Pomegranate Powder is made from freeze-dried juice and seeds.

Depending on the application, the market is divided into juice drinks, pastries, jams, smoothies and puddings; depending on the region - North America, Latin America, Europe, Asia-Pacific, Middle East and Africa.

It is expected that all these markets will grow over the next few years, as pomegranate powder has many health benefits and can be used in various food formulations, such as bakery products, cakes, cookies, etc.

The main players/companies in this market are Navitas Organics, BioFinest, Okami Bio, Nubeleaf, SV Agro Food, Shreedha Phyto Extracts, Rainbow Expochem Company, Vee Natural, Organicway".

Minimally processed pomegranate grains, as well as other products, are becoming increasingly popular among a certain part of consumers, and therefore, the global market of pomegranate fruits and grains amounted to 8.2 billion. \$US in 2018 and is expected to reach 23.14 billion. \$US by 2026 (with an annual growth rate of 14%) [15].

European consumers are increasingly expressing a preference for fruits that are easy to prepare and easy to consume. Therefore, supermarkets sell not only whole pomegranates, but also their aryl grains, both fresh and in the form of a frozen product.

The extension of the period of keeping pomegranate seeds in a fresh state is possible only with the use of advanced technology for packing them in closed bags with a controlled atmosphere (see stock photo below), which can be characterized as a factor somewhat constraining the export of pomegranate seeds. And the advantage of their producers is that pomegranate seeds can be obtained from fruits with superficial external defects.

Stock photo:

Pomegranate seeds from the Netherlands at a price of € 20.00 /100 g. AH Zongerijp-te granaatappelpitjes: [website]. URL:

https://www.ah.nl/producten/product/wi388475/ahzongerijpte-granaatappelpitjes?gclid=EA1aIQobChMIpa3HssLX1wIVBLftCh3gsA-oEAQYAyABEGi6YPD_BwE

In the American and European media, pomegranates are classified as "super fruit" (The best way to open the pomegranate, a super fruit. The Washington Post [website] – URL: https://www.washingtonpost.com/national/health-science/the-best-way-to-open-the-pomegranate-a-super-fruit/2014/01/13/8feee432-7551-11e3-8b3f-b1666705ca3b_story.html?noredirect=on&utm_term=432bdea02705).

In the USA and in Europe, they are valued and referred to as a healthy diet (Wikipedia: [website]-URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Punicic_acid).

Pomegranate peel extracts contain simple phenols and their glycosides and flavonoids, as well as hydrolyzable tannins based on gallic and ellagic acids, which are divided accordingly into gallotanins and ellagitanins.

Among pomegranate polyphenols, ellagitanins are of particular importance due to their antioxidant, antimicrobial and antiradical activity.

Pomegranate ellagitanins have antioxidant, antimicrobial and antiradical activity. This is a family of phenolic compounds, including punicalagins with the chemical formula C₄₈H₂₈O₃₀, a molar mass of 1084.71 g/mol, as well as other derivatives of ellagic acid.

Punicalagins α and β - anomers are the predominant ellagitanins in pomegranate juice and are responsible for its antioxidant properties. However, these substances only in general combination with other ellagitanins, such as ellagic acid and its glycosylated derivatives, other pomegranate ellagitanins, create an important synergistic effect that increases the health benefits of juice.

Punicalagins α and β -anomers are mainly present in the peel of pomegranate fruits, from which they pass

into the primary juice during pressing to extract juice, punicalagins α and β should not be confused with another compound from the ellagitanin group – punicalin with the chemical formula $C_{34}H_{22}O_{22}$, molar mass 782.525.

The norms for the use of pomegranate powder extracts are regulated in accordance with their pharmacological effect. For the sum of pomegranate polyphenols, these are 21; 43 and 86 mg /kg/day; punicalagin, separately -2.1; 4.2 and 85 mg/kg / day; punicalin -5.2; 10.5 and 21 mg /kg/ day. and ellagic acid - 2.0; 3.9 and 7.8 mg /kg/day. 100 g of pomegranate seeds contain 35-75 mg of ellagitanins (ETs) and ellagic acid (EA).

The group of biologically active substances called pomegranate ellagitanins, along with punicalagin and punicalin, also includes corilagin, granatin A, granatin B, pedunculagin, punicalcortin A, punicalcortin B, punicalcortin C, punicalcortin D, punicalfolin, puniglucolin, tellimagrandin I, tellimagrandin II and terminalin/ gallaglyldylactone.

The antioxidant capacity of food products is usually measured by the ORAC scale (Oxygen Radical Absorption Capacity), developed at the National Institute for the Study of Aging (The National Institute of Aging) in Maryland, USA. Considering that the antioxidant capacity of pomegranate on the ORAC scale is approximately 4451, and the daily recommended adult rate of ORAC is 3000-5000, it can be considered that pomegranate is an exceptionally useful product that prevents the aging process.

The peel and seeds of pomegranate vary greatly in their texture and composition, given this, some companies that are closer to the production of dietary supplements than to the food sector have created their own lines from prefabricated equipment for the separate processing of peel and seeds with the release of polyphenols from the peel, oil from seeds. Although such a scheme is multifaceted, and the utilization rate of raw materials in it is very low, these companies still manage to compensate with a high price for targeted extracts - polyphenols of the peel and seed oil.

Currently, several such companies are operating [16-17].

The company POM Wonderful USA (California) produces 100% concentrated pomegranate juice and a product with the brand name POM x - a highly concentrated aqueous mixture of polyphenolic antioxidants derived from California pomegranates, which is used as an ingredient for plant-based antioxidants and dyes [18].

Stock Photo:
POM Pomegranate
Extract Herbal One.
URL:
[https://karambola-](https://karambola-shop.ru/product/ekstrakt-granata-pom-pomegranate-extract-herbal-one/)

[shop.ru/product/ekstrakt-granata-pom-pomegranate-extract-herbal-one/](https://karambola-shop.ru/product/ekstrakt-granata-pom-pomegranate-extract-herbal-one/)

POM Wonderful is one of the strongest marketing companies of garnet (below is a stock photo of one of its products).

Below is a stock photo of Life Extension pomegranate extract, it is recommended to use it to improve heart health and normalize blood pressure. These are 60 vegetarian capsules; each capsule contains 200 mg of pomegranate extract in powder; retail price \$19.90.

Stock photo:
Pomegranate fruit extract
from Life Extension.
Vitamin Global: [website] -
URL: [https://](https://www.vitaminglobal.com/kosher-lmehadrin-pomegranate-extract-60-capsules-supherb-p-2320-c-7_37_38.html#.YyIMjnVBzDc)

www.vitaminglobal.com/kosher-lmehadrin-pomegranate-extract-60-capsules-supherb-p-2320-c-7_37_38.html#.YyIMjnVBzDc.

In online stores, you can buy Pomella extract, standardized by 30% punicalagins content. These are 60 (\$21.99) or 120 (\$37.99) vegetarian capsules, each of which allegedly contains the power of 30 pomegranates. It is recommended to take one (1) capsule daily with or without food, or as recommended by a doctor. It is claimed that it can protect against atherosclerosis, aging, slow down the progression of cancer. However, these claims have not been officially confirmed. Recommendations for its use are based only on consumer reviews, which gave the extract a high rating in the treatment of prostate cancer.

Stock Photo: Pamela
Pomegranate Extract from
Verdure Sciences /Capsules
150 mg (120 Count)|Oxidative
and Inflammatory Support
Supplement| Promotes Cardiovascular Health. URL:
[https://vs-corp.com/pomella /](https://vs-corp.com/pomella/).

The technology of Pomella ® extract is protected by patent US7638640 [19], which is dedicated to the compositions of pomegranate ellagitanins and methods for obtaining such compositions, as well as their application. Ellagitanins are extracted by extraction, purified by a series of extractions of the "solvent from solvent" type or using a method involving passing the solution through chromatographic columns with solid polymer adsorbents.

Another company actively using pomegranate is the Spanish company Probelebio, famous for its Pomanox extract, which is manufactured using extraction technology, patented at the European Patent Office [20]. The invention provides several advantages over the methods of the previous state of the art. Since the extraction stage of ellagitanins is carried out from the entire pomegranate fruit, not only polyphenols of the peel, but also other fruit parts fall into the extract. In addition, it is carried out with acidified water at room temperature simultaneously with fruit grinding and is completed in about one hour and without significant transition to the aqueous phase of by-products such as free ellagic acid.

Pharmachem Laboratories (a subsidiary of American Ingredients), which is the exclusive distributor for Pomanox, is trying to stand out with this extract in the US pomegranate extracts market. The fact that Pomanox is water-soluble makes it ideal for use in beverage mixes, while it also has good heat resistance and a neutral taste.

It is significant that in this invention and in other industrially applied inventions, the selective extraction of elagitanins from a mixture of polyphenols is carried out using sorbents or chromatography.

The company Life Extension (USA) supplies its extract with the name Pomella, which contains up to 30% punicalagins, to the pomegranate extracts market. The same company produces an extract from a mixture of fruits, seed oil and pomegranate flower extracts, one capsule of which contains polyphenols, the amount of which is equivalent to 360 ml (12 ounces) of pomegranate juice.

The Chinese company Huan Greeland Plant Resource Development CoşÇ Ltd produces pomegranate extracts with a content of 10 to 40% punicalagins by high-performance liquid chromatography.

On the market of pomegranate extracts, you can find an extract in packages with a different number of capsules containing 500 mg of ellagic acid in each capsule from India, which costs from 10.86 to 72.63 US dollars; pomegranate seed extract containing 40% polyphenols from the UK, which costs from 10.28 to 72.63 US dollars.

Obtaining powdered tannin (a mixture of polyphenols) small Chinese manufacturers are engaged in pomegranate peel. The Indian company "Freeze Foods" has been producing powder from direct grinding of dried peel since 1960, recommending adding it to tea, using it as an elite feed additive, in the manufacture of tooth powders and pastes, as part of skin care products. In Moscow stores "Products from nature" you can also find pomegranate crusts at a price of \$ 5.4/200 g.

The global polyphenols market amounted to \$580 million in 2011, \$873.7 million in 2018, \$1121 million in 2022, and its further growth is expected.

The largest producers of polyphenols are Naturex, Layn Natural Ingredients, DuPont-Danisco, ADM, Ajinomoto Omnicem Natural Specialties, Barry Callebaut, PROVA, and CEMOI are few major companies in the competitive scenario market.

Other prominent players (not profiled in this report) are Indena S.P.A., Frutarom Ltd, Martin Bauer Group, DSM, HERZA Schokolade GMBH & Co. KG, Futureceuticals, Glanbia Nutritionals, Amax NutraSource Inc, Sabinsa Corporation, Kemin Health, Cargill Inc, Blue California, and Fruitomed.

The global volume of pomegranate concentrates (which are used for the production of pomegranate juice, food, medicines, etc.) produced in 2022 is estimated at \$248.4 million; with an average annual growth rate of 5.3% over the reporting period, it should reach \$338.6 million by 2028 [21].

Stiebs company (USA), engaged in the production of fruit ingredients, in 2011 launched a new line for the

production of pomegranate ingredients, which are presented to the world market as natural food additives. The line is designed to produce pomegranate seed oil and peel extract. The oil is squeezed from the seeds after they are dried and crushed, intended for use for cosmetic purposes. The extract is a water-soluble antioxidant powder for use as an additive in cosmetic products, as well as beverages and other food products. The product has a beneficial effect on the heart, the content of polyphenols is standardized by 50%.

Oils from the seeds of superfruits such as baobab, acai and pomegranate are especially popular in cosmetics, as they are high in omega-3 and omega-7 fatty acids. Pomegranate seed oil revives the growth of dry and fading hair, cleanses the scree of the scalp, promotes hair growth and nourishes them, shows anti-purification properties.

The macroeconomic factors that lead to the global growth of the Punica granatum L. seed oil market are the rapid pace of urbanization, lifestyle changes and economic growth in countries such as China, Brazil, India. These three countries and Argentina determine the positive growth rate of the global pomegranate seed oil market, since here it is used not only for medicinal purposes and as a skin and hair care product, but also together with vegetables. Another factor is the fast-growing nutraceutical and cosmetic industry.

According to Future market insights, [22], the value of the pomegranate seed oil market increased from 473.8 million US dollars in 2017 to 567.2 million US dollars in 2021. The real value is expected to increase from US\$593.3 million in 2022 to US\$ 861.5 million in 2032.

The competitive environment in the pomegranate seed oil market is highly fragmented by a large number of small and medium-sized players. The key players are POM Wonderful, Fyffes and Hain Celestial Group.

POM Wonderful is the largest player in the market with a market share of 36%, the company has a strong influence in the USA and Europe. Fyffes accounts for 20% of the market, the company has a strong influence in Europe and South America. In addition to these companies, such companies as St. Francis, Herb Farm Inc, W. ULRICH GMBH, All Organic Treasures GMBH, Ario fruit co, rEALOE LTD, Aznar, b PARODI NUTRA S.R.L. are also involved in the market.

Now, cold-pressed pomegranate seed oil is sold in online stores at a price of about \$ 20/50 ml, and subcritical and supercritical CO₂ seed extracts are \$ 5-6/10 ml (and when searching, it turned out that many stores do not have them at the moment). One package of high-quality extract from the selective extraction of punicalagins from the whole pomegranate fruit "Nutri Care Pomanox Pomegranate Extract" (60 capsules) costs \$ 55, and pomegranate peel extract from Chinese manufacturers in the form of a dark powder with 60% total polyphenols content costs \$ 19.1/kg.

The main drawback of single-product technologies for processing pomegranate peel and seeds

After receiving polyphenols and oil, the bulk of the peel and seeds of pomegranate does not go away,

only new waste is formed in the form of a fat-free residue of the peel and fat-free seeds. This is a big drawback that the aforementioned firms and companies are still able to compensate for the high price of pomegranate extracts and oil.

From the point of view of effective management, such a prudent attitude to raw materials cannot be acceptable.

Food producers, who have to process pomegranates by thousands of tons, are waiting for the appearance on the markets of technological equipment of ready-made lines for fast and clean (without residue) processing of industrial residues of this type, which could ensure the return of a significant part of the costs that were already incurred by the time of their formation in the process of obtaining pomegranate juice.

Fig. The product line from the separation of pomegranate fruits into separate parts and their step-by-step processing according to patent RU No. 2712602 [23].

From Fig. it can be seen that the phased processing of pomegranate can give, along with juice, several more popular products.

It is possible that these may initially be semi-finished products intended for further processing, and away from the place of their production. AZGRANATA LLC (Ahsu, Azerbaijan) operates in this direction. The pomegranate seed drying section is already functioning here: it includes Turkish-made equipment for cleaning, drying with natural gas, cleaning from impurities with a sieve and packing in bags of 800 kg. The resulting product is exported to various countries for the preparation of cosmetic and pharmaceutical preparations.

Conclusion

Thus, the review of the known methods of fractionation of medicinal and biologically active compounds of solid by-products of pomegranate juice production showed that the approach leading to the

sequential production of several values seems to be a promising alternative for their valorization.

The peel and seeds left over after obtaining the juice from pomegranate fruits are valuable sources of bioactive phytochemicals, the vast majority of which have great potential to be converted into value-added products. These by-products can be used as a substrate for the production of nutritionally valuable and biologically active components, which could find several applications as functional food ingredients, food additives, nutraceuticals and additives and in diets rich in phenol.

Since the formation of peel and seeds or fruit pulp during the production of pomegranate juice is an inevitable process, all costs incurred at the time of their formation are included in the cost of juice, which suggests that the processes of their further processing should be economically profitable.

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